

EBFMC25-OP-10 · Isolated Abducens Nerve Palsy Secondary to Diabetes in a Patient Presenting with Esotropia

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Microvascular causes such as diabetes, hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, and hyperlipidemia are the most common etiological factors encountered in abducens nerve palsy.

Case Presentation: Although ophthalmoplegia is a rare but well-recognized complication of diabetes, studies have shown that the risk is higher in individuals with diabetes compared to non-diabetics.

Discussion: Acute ocular cranial neuropathies associated with microvascular ischemia are generally believed to resolve spontaneously within an average of 3 to 5 months.

Conclusion: However, investigating and managing microvascular risk factors is essential to prevent subsequent attacks, which may be more severe or even life-threatening.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Abducens nerve, esotropia, diabetes

INTRODUCTION

The abducens nerve (sixth cranial nerve, CN VI) innervates the lateral rectus muscle. The nucleus of the abducens nerve is located in the dorsal pons, and the nerve exits at the pontomedullary junction, passing at an angle from the petrous portion of the temporal bone. It then enters the cavernous sinus via the Dorello canal, courses beneath the internal carotid artery within the sinus, and finally enters the orbit through the superior orbital fissure to innervate the lateral rectus muscle (Ambekar et al., 2012; Geçirilmesi, 2008). Among all cranial nerves, the abducens nerve has the longest intracranial course. Dysfunction of the sixth cranial nerve can result from lesions occurring anywhere along its pathway, from the abducens nucleus in the dorsal pons to the lateral rectus muscle within the orbit. Abducens nerve palsy has an incidence of 11.3 per 100.000 individuals. It is the most common cranial neuropathy in adults, with the highest prevalence observed in individuals aged 60–70 years (Patel et al., 2004). In addition to diplopia, it may also be accompanied by headache or periorbital pain. The most common etiology of abducens nerve palsy is microvascular causes, which are particularly prevalent in older adults (Elder et al., 2016). In one study, hypertension was identified as the most frequent microvascular risk factor, present in 71% of cases, followed by diabetes (54%), hypercholesterolemia (48%), and hyperlipidemia (53%) (Sanders, Kawasaki, & Purvin, 2002). Another study reported diabetes as the most common underlying cause (Erdal, Gunes, & Emre, 2022). Other significant causes of abducens nerve palsy include trauma, demyelinating or inflammatory diseases (such as Tolosa-Hunt syndrome), infections, tumors, aneurysms, and increased intracranial pressure (Elder et al., 2016; Patel et al., 2004). Abducens nerve dysfunction results in unilateral abduction deficiency and binocular horizontal diplopia (Patel et al., 2004). Patients typically present to an ophthalmologist with new onset esotropia and diplopia. In this study, we present a case of isolated abducens nerve palsy resulting from microvascular damage secondary to diabetes.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 54-year-old female patient presented to our clinic with complaints of esotropia and diplopia in her left eye, persisting for two months. She did not report any accompanying headache or periorbital pain. There was no history of trauma, systemic malignancy, surgery, or oral/genital ulcers. Her medical history included amblyopia in the left eye and diabetes mellitus. Best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) was 0.8 in the right eye and "2 meters per second" (mps) in the left eye. Both eyes exhibited normal direct and indirect pupillary light reflexes, and pupil size was normal. The right eye was orthotropic, while the left eye exhibited esotropia (Figure 1). Ocular motility examination revealed -2 limitation in abduction of the left eye, while upward, downward, and inward movements were normal (Figure 2). The range of eye movements were free in all directions.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Upon evaluating the presence of binocular and monocular diplopia, diplopia was observed in left gaze. Slit-lamp examination revealed a normal anterior segment bilaterally. Dilated fundus examination showed microhemorrhages and exudates in the retina bilaterally, while the optic disc appeared normal (Figure 3a, 3b). The retinal findings were consistent with non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR). Fundus fluorescein angiography (FFA) demonstrated bilateral hyperfluorescence due to microaneurysms, with no evidence of ischemia or neovascularization.

Figure 3a

Figure 3b

The patient was diagnosed with isolated left abducens nerve palsy and was referred to the neurology clinic for further etiological evaluation. Additional laboratory tests were planned to investigate the underlying cause, including complete blood count (CBC), biochemistry panel, HbA1c, cholesterol and lipid panel, erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), C-reactive protein (CRP), and serologic tests for HSV-II IgG/IgM, HSV-I IgG/IgM, and VZV IgG/IgM. Neurological examination and cranial imaging performed by the neurology clinic were evaluated as normal, and no neurological etiology was identified. Laboratory results revealed an HbA1c level of 7.50. Other laboratory results were normal.

Given the presence of uncontrolled diabetes and findings consistent with non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR), along with the exclusion of other potential etiologies, we concluded that the isolated left abducens nerve palsy was a result of microvascular damage secondary to diabetes. Based on the fundus examination, optical coherence tomography (OCT), and fundus fluorescein angiography (FFA) findings, the patient was diagnosed with non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy, and blood glucose regulation was recommended. Close follow-up was advised for both diabetic retinopathy and left abducens nerve palsy. At the two-month follow-up examination, the previous esotropia in the left eye had regressed, and ocular movements were normal in all nine gaze positions (Figure 4). The abducens nerve palsy had resolved (Figure 5).

Figure 4

Figure 5

DISCUSSION

Although abducens nerve palsy is a common condition in neurological practice, considering its anatomical course and etiological factors, diagnosis may initially appear straightforward in isolated cases without other neurological findings. However, the presence of multiple potential etiologies with similar clinical manifestations can pose challenges in differential diagnosis. As demonstrated in various studies, the sixth cranial nerve palsy is the most frequently observed cranial nerve palsy in ophthalmoplegia (Al Kahtani et al.,

2016). The high incidence of CN VI palsy is most likely attributed to its long intracranial course, which makes it more susceptible to ischemia due to angiopathic changes (Azarmina & Azarmina, 2013). A 15-year retrospective study investigating the underlying causes of abducens nerve palsy found that 35% of cases were associated with hypertension, with diabetes being a less frequent cause. Additionally, 26% of cases were idiopathic, 7% were due to multiple sclerosis, 5% were attributed to neoplasms, and 2% were linked to aneurysms (Patel et al., 2004). Studies conducted in the United States, France, and the United Kingdom have supported the finding that the sixth cranial nerve is the most commonly affected nerve in diabetic patients (Tiffin et al., 1996; Trigler et al., 2003). Although ophthalmoplegia is a well-recognized but rare complication of diabetes, it has been reported to occur 10 times more frequently in diabetic individuals compared to non-diabetic individuals (Watanabe et al., 1990). Both NPDR and PDR with macular edema (ME) have been identified as significant risk factors for ophthalmoplegia (Al Kahtani et al., 2016; Oštrić et al., 2011). With advancements in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), the identification of treatable etiologies such as intracranial neoplasms, aneurysms, inflammation, infections, and brainstem infarctions has become more feasible, allowing for more timely treatment of acute ocular cranial neuropathies (Lee et al., 2002). On the other hand, some researchers argue that early neuroimaging may not be necessary in cases of isolated sixth nerve palsy accompanied by vascular risk factors, suggesting that imaging should only be performed if the patient's clinical condition does not improve within three months (Chan & Albretson, 2015; Murchison et al., 2011).

Although acute ocular cranial neuropathies associated with microvascular ischemia are generally thought to resolve spontaneously within an average of 3–5 months, it is crucial to investigate and manage microvascular risk factors to prevent more severe or even life-threatening events. It should be kept in mind that abducens nerve palsy, although rare, can occur as a complication in diabetic patients.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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